

A Rare Case of Anaphylaxis Following Intravenous Hyoscine-N-butylbromide Administration

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Dear Editor,

Hyoscine-N-butylbromide (HBB) is a drug widely used to resolve smooth muscle spasms in the gastrointestinal tract, biliary tract and urinary tract due to its potent anticholinergic effects (1). HBB, especially under the trade name Buscopan®, is frequently preferred in emergency departments (EDs) because of its antispasmodic effects. The fact that the drug is generally well tolerated and that its side effects are mostly mild and self-limiting are the main reasons for its widespread use. Common side effects include dry mouth, tachycardia, blurred vision, and skin reactions (2).

However, the number of cases of serious adverse reactions related to HBB in literature is limited. In particular, reports of serious complications such as hypotension, myocardial ischemia, and anaphylaxis indicate the need for caution during clinical use of this drug (2,3). Consideration of these rare serious adverse effects of drugs in clinical decision-making processes is vital for patient safety. In this context, elaboration of rare but potentially serious effects of HBB in the literature with more case reports will contribute to increasing awareness of such events and to the development of clinical management strategies.

Accordingly, we aimed to contribute to the clinical management and awareness of these rare adverse events by

reporting anaphylactic reactions following intravenous HBB administration in our ED.

CASE PRESENTATION

A 74-year-old woman presented to our ED with abdominal pain and diarrhea that began after a meal. Her medical history included hypertension, coronary artery disease (CAD), asthma, hypothyroidism, and hyperlipidemia. On admission, the patient's vital signs were as follows: temperature, 36.6°C; blood pressure, 120/70 mmHg; pulse rate: 76/min and oxygen saturation, 98%. Physical examination revealed no abdominal defense or rebound tenderness. With a prediagnosis of acute gastroenteritis, symptomatic treatment was planned, and 1 ampoule of Buscopan was administered intravenously in 500 cc saline. However, the patient developed sudden hypotension (70/50 mmHg) and hypoxia (84%) during the treatment. In addition, the patient developed anaphylaxis symptoms, including tremors and dizziness. The treatment was immediately discontinued, and the patient received intramuscular adrenaline 0.5 mg and intravenous fluid support. The patient was monitored and kept under observation for eight

hours. The patient became hemodynamically stable during the follow-up period and was discharged with cure.

CONCLUSION

This case highlights that, in addition to the usually mild and self-limiting side effects of HBB, rare but serious adverse effects can also occur. The limited number of case reports documenting adverse effects of HBB in the literature indicates that these effects should not be ignored and that such situations should be handled with caution in clinical practice. This drug, which is widely used in EDs, should be closely monitored for potentially life-threatening side effects, such as anaphylactic reactions. In addition, the preparation of appropriate treatment protocols and availability of emergency response equipment will play a critical role in increasing patient safety.

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